

SELECTION OF ITS SOLUTIONS FOR IMPROVING THE QUALITY OF THE TRAFFIC SYSTEM IN THE CITY OF ZAGREB BASED ON USER REQUIREMENTS

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1. Introduction

The quality of the transport system in cities is significantly improved using intelligent transport systems (ITS), which implies the use of advanced telematic solutions and other technologies. ITS can be defined as a holistic and information communication superstructure of the classic traffic and transport system, which can achieve a significant improvement in traffic flow, more efficient transport, increase in traffic safety, comfort and protection of passengers, less environmental pollution, etc. (Bošnjak, 2006). In the initial reference model for the ITS sector, 11 functional areas and 32 services were defined. Some of these functional areas are passenger information, traffic management, driver assistance and vehicle control.

The implementation of intelligent solutions makes it possible to fulfil user requirements for a given system, such as the optimization of adaptive traffic light systems, the traffic management centre, the public transport (PT) passenger information system, giving unconditional priority to urgent services, the automatic payment system for entrance to the city centre, and the park & ride system.

Sensors and detectors are key technical components of ITS that enable data collection from source systems. The sensor represents the input and output of the system that can react to light, heat, pressure, electric or magnetic field, and gas so that it produces a signal about the state of the medium where it is located. The output is usually an electrical signal that is further processed and transmitted to the control part of the system (Ezgeta, 2018).

All collected data can be processed at the same level and provide a solution based on the current state. For the optimal operation of the entire system, the centralization of the data would lead to a greater impact on the entire transport system. Some obstacles faced by this topic are that such a centre does not exist, different stakeholders in terms of disciplines are needed to run a centralized system, separate companies that own data are not willing to share with each other and data processing itself would be challenging due to the amount and different formats of records.

2. Survey results and analysis

In the paper, a survey was conducted to find out from the users what would be the ideal solution to improve the traffic system of the city of Zagreb. In total, there were about 150 respondents in the area of Zagreb and its surroundings. Originally, the survey collected data about the person filling out the survey. This includes information about the person's age, gender, and employment. In the survey, participants were asked to describe which form of transport they use and how often they travel to Zagreb. Knowledge of various terms such as Intelligent Transport Systems, Old Town Entrance Fee, Park & Ride, Main Traffic Centre was especially fulfilling. In the next phase of the survey, people expressed their opinion on the current state of the transport system, satisfaction with the transport system in the city of Zagreb in the centre and surroundings, whether public city transport provides users with reliable information when travelling, the level of satisfaction with the work of emergency services and whether it is necessary to introduce the main traffic control centre.

The conducted survey revealed that a large proportion of people are between 20 and 40 years old. By examining users about their gender, it was determined that 55.62% of respondents were men, while 44.37% were women. The largest share of respondents use public transport and a personal vehicle as the primary means of transport, while transport by train and other means is poorly represented. According to the respondents, the quality of the traffic system of the city of Zagreb was rated with an average rating of 3.13. when choosing a grade, there is a small concentration of excellent (5) and very poor grades (1). The quality of traffic management within the core of the city of Zagreb was also rated with an average rating of 3.04. Among the respondents, 88.08% are of the opinion that the traffic system in the city of Zagreb needs to be reorganized. Public city transport was evaluated with an average score of 3.07, while the reliability of informing passengers in transport is not considered sufficiently reliable by 56.60% of respondents. In the context of public city transport, the vast majority (94.70%) believe that it is necessary to improve the tram and bus system, and they also believe that the quality of the displayed real time data should be improved. The majority opinion of the respondents shows that right-of-way should be added to public city transport, especially in the old city core. The quality rating of emergency services is 3.43, while their response to incidents is considered acceptable. 52.98% of respondents knew the concept of the main traffic centre, and 86.75% of them believed that it is needed in the city of Zagreb.

3. Possible ITS solution

Considering the collected data, a solution is found that is ideal for improving the traffic system of the city of Zagreb. Using the analytical hierarchy process method, it is found that the centre for data processing and traffic management is the best in all aspects compared to other solutions.

The centre for data processing and traffic management is a facility that is fully cooperative with the traffic infrastructure and connected by numerous cameras, sensors, detectors and other communication methods. Data processing performed within the control centre is in real-time, which enables easier management of the entire traffic network and insight into possible traffic congestion and incidents. The monitoring centre monitors almost the entire traffic network and sends users the necessary information and redirects them as needed. The control centre has the

ability to communicate with users via radio connection, electronic signs or via mobile devices that must be connected to the Internet or Bluetooth in advance.

The entire system consists of a input subsystem (entire sensors, detectors, inductive loops, video surveillance), a communication subsystem (Bluetooth connection, wireless 4G, radio connection) and an infrastructure subsystem (objects closely related to the control centre) (Vidaković, 2017).

4. Data collection processes

One of the main systems applied in the city of Zagreb through which data would be collected on the state of the part of the traffic system in which the device is located are: electronic bulletin boards, ticket registration, smart garages, interactive electronic panels, pedestrian buttons and navigation systems - GPS navigation (Bošnjak, 2006).

Data on public city transport traffic would be collected in the data processing and traffic management centre from ticket registration devices, electronic billboards, interactive electronic panels, and GPS navigation of individual public city transport entities.

Electronic billboards are located at terminals, tram and bus stations where each billboard has the option of displaying passenger information about the current traffic situation, significant changes in the timetable and cancellation of PT lines (United States Department of Transportation, 2022). Information that can be found on the screen includes the arrival and departure times of a particular bus or tram line, the identification number of the next PT vehicle and other information for that line. The terminal would coordinate the same data with the centre for data processing and traffic management using some of the wireless communication methods.

Interactive electronic panels are computer circuits with appropriate software that enables insight into timetables, possible delays, the current position of PT vehicles, a map with stops and terminals, and the annexation of passengers. At the same time, they enable the display of information to the carrier, ticket prices and weather information. The most common places where interactive panels are installed are terminals, but also in infrastructure assemblies at PT stops or as an independent object. The data it would display would be synchronized with the data processing and traffic management centre.

The GPS coordinates of individual traffic entities of public city transport would also be available to the centre for data processing and traffic management and, in combination with other data from various sensors and detectors, would show the real time state of the traffic network.

Smart public garages are a special form of garages that, first of all, provide users with information about the number of free spaces, and in advanced versions, users are guided to the parking space. In addition to the technology used in ordinary garages (ramp, card printer), "smart" has been added, which has a known number of free spaces in the garage and compares them with the entrance and exit of vehicles and shows everything on the LCD display when entering the garage. The distance sensor scans the distance and reports to the central computer whether the place is free or occupied. By adding a camera at the entrance and exit, it is possible to scan the registration to make it easier to miss the vehicle when leaving the garage. Navigation through the garage is made possible by an LCD display that directs certain cars with an arrow to a free space. This type of system generally

reduces waiting times and crowds inside the garage, but it could also be useful in a wider traffic area. Using the data of the smart garage system, the traffic management centre could optimize the load on garages at the level of the city of Zagreb, thereby redirecting a certain number of vehicles to zones with less traffic load.

5. Conclusion

Having that said, using devices for data collection at the intersection, such as cameras, pedestrian button counters and other sensors and detectors, would enable the data processing and traffic management centre to have a better overview of the traffic situation in the city of Zagreb. Access to this data would enable traffic to be adjusted to the actual situation. In addition, they would thereby contribute to the reduction of the environmental impact of traffic on the environment, increasing both safety and passenger satisfaction.

After the definition of the present state of traffic management in urban areas, it is possible to conclude that such an element is needed for the optimisation and regulation of urban traffic networks. Because a large amount of data can be gathered from the traffic network, it is essential to open the collected datasets for wide usage for all involved stakeholders and for end users. Traffic data on this higher level of openness provides the basis for the development and implementation of advanced ITS solutions designed for the improvement of the urban traffic network. Future research will be focused on the allocation of relevant traffic data which must be opened and to what extent. Also, with the opening of allocated data, which ITS solutions in urban areas can be upgraded and implemented for a better urban traffic network quality.

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References

- Bošnjak, I. (2006). *Inteligentni transportni sustavi -ITS 1*. Faculty of Transport and Traffic Sciences, University of Zagreb, Zagreb.
- Ezgeta, D. (2018). *Inteligentni transportni sustavi*. Faculty of Traffic and Communications, University of Sarajevo, Sarajevo.
- U.S. Department of Transportation (2020). *Benefits of intelligent transportation systems (ITS)*. Available at https://www.its.dot.gov/factsheets/pdf/Benefits_FactSheet.pdf. Accessed June 2, 2020.
- Vidaković, F. (2017). *Concept of development center to monitor and manage traffic in cities (in Croatian)*. Graduation thesis. Faculty of Transport and Traffic Sciences, University of Zagreb, Zagreb.